

Thallimetric Oxidations. Part-VIII. Titrimetric and Spectrophotometric Methods for the Estimation of Mesoxalic Acid

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Volumetric determination of mesoxalic acid by phenylhydrazine method¹ and the microdetermination of mesoxalic acid and related compounds have been reported². Jwo and Noyes³ reported the quantitative oxidation of mesoxalic acid to carbon dioxide and water in the presence of excess of cerium(IV). These methods are cumbersome and time-consuming. The authors now report the reaction between mesoxalic acid and thallium(III) and describe convenient titrimetric and spectrophotometric methods for the determination of mesoxalic acid in mmol and μ mol ranges respectively.

Results and Discussion

Photochemical oxidation of mesoxalic acid :

The effect of light on the oxidation of mesoxalic acid by thallium(III) is studied. The time required for the oxidation of mesoxalic acid decreased with increase in $[Tl^{III}]$ and decrease in $[acid]$. Mesoxalic acid does not interfere in the bromatometric titration⁴ of Tl^I . Hence, this titration was utilised for monitoring the progress of the reaction. The stoichiometry of the reaction is given as

The concentration of Tl^{III} should be at least eight times to that required for quantitative oxidation for a quick progress of the reaction and further increase in $[Tl^{III}]$ has no noticeable effect on the reaction. However, the same stoichiometry is obtained even with less Tl^{III} but the reaction gets slowed down. In the presence of optimum Tl^{III} in 1.0 M perchloric acid, the reaction goes to completion in about 120 min. Under these condi-

tions the effect of halide ions on the reaction is studied. Fluoride has no effect while chloride retards the oxidation of mesoxalic acid and bromide catalyses the reaction. The effect of bromide and acid concentration on the photochemical oxidation of mesoxalic acid is studied. The results show that the optimal bromide concentration for the quick progress of the reaction is half that of Tl^{III} and under these conditions the reaction is complete in one min.

By maintaining Tl^{III} to bromide ratio as 2 : 1, the effects of Tl^{III} and acid concentrations on the reaction are studied. The results indicate that when the concentration of perchloric acid is 0.5 to 1.0 M and $[Tl^{III}]$ twice that required for complete oxidation of mesoxalic acid, quantitative oxidation takes place within 7 min. Based on the above observation a titrimetric procedure is described for the estimation of mesoxalic acid.

The method : To an aliquot containing 0.025 mmol of mesoxalic acid were added sufficient perchloric acid (so that the overall concentration in the final reaction mixture was 1.0 M), Tl^{III} (1.0 mmol) and bromide (0.5 mmol). The solution was diluted to 100 ml and exposed to the light from a mercury vapour lamp for 10 min, then concentrated HCl (15 ml) and a 0.1% methyl orange indicator solution (0.1 ml) were added. The solution was heated to 60° and titrated with 0.00829 M potassium bromate (1.392 g dm⁻³). The amount of mesoxalic acid was computed from the amount of Tl^I formed. The results obtained by following the procedure, given below, show that the method is quite satisfactory and applicable in sulphuric acid medium also.

Thermal oxidation of mesoxalic acid :

The reaction between mesoxalic acid and thallium(III) is investigated in sulphuric acid medium only, as perchloric acid is susceptible to explosion at higher temperatures especially in the presence of organic compounds. At room temperature, the reaction is not completed even after two days. The oxidation of mesoxalic acid by Tl^{III} goes to completion, under reflux, when a minimum of double the theoretical amount of Tl^{III} to that required for complete oxidation of mesoxalic acid is present in the reaction mixture. The time of thermal oxidation was found to decrease with increase in Tl^{III} and acid concentrations. When Tl^{III} is present at least eight times to that required for complete oxidation of mesoxalic acid in 1 to 1.5 M sulphuric acid medium, the reaction goes to completion in 30 min. Based on these observations, a simple and convenient procedure is recommended for the estimation of mesoxalic acid.

The method : To an aliquot containing 0.025–0.25 mmol of mesoxalic acid, were added sufficient amount of sulphuric acid (so that the overall concentration of the final mixture became 1.0 M), Tl^{III} (2.0 mmol) and diluted to 100 ml. It was refluxed for 30 min at 95–100°, then cooled to 60° and the amount of mesoxalic acid was determined as mentioned above. The results are given in Table 1.

Spectrophotometric method for the determination of mesoxalic acid :

The thallimetric oxidation method is extended for the development of a spectrophotometric method for the estimation of mesoxalic acid. The absorption spectra⁵ of Tl^I and Tl^{III} in 1 M perchloric acid and 0.1 M sodium chloride medium show that Tl^{III} has considerable absorption at 250 nm (molar absorptivity $9.15 \times 10^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) while Tl^I does not show any absorbance. The presence of mesoxalic acid does not affect the absorption spectrum of Tl^{III} under these conditions and the Tl^{III} species obey Beer's law at 260 nm. An excess of Tl^{III} is allowed to react with mesoxalic acid photochemically (with bromide as catalyst). The amount of mesoxalic acid in the test sample corresponds to the amount of Tl^{III} reduced to Tl^I , which can

TABLE 1—ESTIMATION OF MESOXALIC ACID BY DIFFERENT METHODS

Mesoxalic acid (mmol)		% Error
Taken	Found	
Photochemical method :		
0.025 0	0.025 0	Nil
0.050 0	0.050 2	0.4
0.080 0	0.079 7	0.3
0.100 0	0.100 2	0.2
0.125 0	0.125 0	Nil
0.150 0	0.150 7	0.5
0.250 0	0.250 7	0.3
Thermal method :		
0.025 0	0.025 0	Nil
0.035 0	0.035 0	Nil
0.050 0	0.049 7	0.6
0.055 0	0.055 2	0.4
0.080 0	0.080 2	0.3
0.100 0	0.100 2	0.2
0.125 0	0.125 2	0.2
Spectrophotometric method :		
Mesoxalic acid (μ mol)		% Error
Taken	Found	
0.200	0.200	Nil
0.400	0.400	Nil
0.500	0.500	Nil
0.700	0.690	1.4
0.900	0.890	1.1
1.200	1.195	0.4

be read from the calibration curve. The method is quite accurate (Table 1). The thermal reaction in perchloric acid is avoided because of potential explosion hazard.

The method : To an aliquot of sample containing 0.2–1.2 mol mesoxalic acid were added 11.6 M perchloric acid (4.3 ml), KBr (2.4 μ mol), 4.0×10^{-4} M Tl^{III} solution (12 ml) and then exposed to the radiation from the mercury vapour lamp for 30 min. To the solution, NaCl (10 ml) solution was added and diluted to 100 ml (Solution-I). A corresponding solution was prepared without mesoxalic acid (Solution-II). After 30 min, the absorbance of Solution-II was measured

against Solution-I as reference at 260 nm. The absorbance corresponded to the Tl^{III} that reacted. A calibration curve was prepared by the same procedure.

Interference : Formic, oxalic, malonic, lactic, tartaric, malic and citric acids interfere in both the thermal and photochemical methods. Acetic, succinic, adipic and pimelic acids do not interfere in the thermal method. The results (Table 1) show that the methods are quite satisfactory. The advantage of the method is that the oxidant is stable and the photochemical reaction is very fast even under mild experimental conditions. Further, even the thermal reaction does not require more than 30 min of reflux time.

The photochemical oxidation of mesoxalic acid proceeds slowly in the absence of a catalyst. In the presence of optimum bromide concentration the photochemical oxidation is complete in 1 min only. Mesoxalic acid can be oxidised to carbon dioxide and water via. (i) oxalic acid or (ii) formic acid or (iii) glyoxylic acid. The oxidation of mesoxalic acid is observed to be fast as the oxidation of oxalic acid⁶. The formation of formic acid can be excluded because for the quantitative oxidation of formic acid more time is required⁷ than that of mesoxalic acid itself. For similar reasons the decarboxylation of mesoxalic acid through glyoxylic acid route can also be excluded⁸. Therefore the route of photochemical oxidation of mesoxalic acid may be given as

Experimental

Thallium(III) hydroxide prepared as reported earlier was dissolved in suitable amount of perchloric or sulphuric acid and the thallium(III) content was esti-

mated^{9,10}. Aqueous solution of mesoxalic acid was prepared and standardised using the reported method³. Aqueous solution of methyl orange indicator (0.1%) was used. All other reagents were of A.R. grade.

Though the photochemical reactions described take place much faster under direct sunlight, in view of its variable intensity, the investigative work described here was done using a Phillips high pressure mercury vapour lamp (200/250V–125W) as the light source. The photochemical reactions were carried out by exposing the solution in colourless glass containers kept at a constant distance of 6 inches from the light source.

A Milton-Roy Spectronic 1201 spectrophotometer with silica cells of 1 cm path-length was used for the absorbance measurements.

References

1. H. HIROYAMA and T. Y. AMANO, *Ann. Rep. Shinogi Res. Lab.*, 1956, **6**, 55
2. E. OCHIAI, T. OKAMATO and T. UEDA, *J. Pharm. Soc. Jpn.*, 1955, **75**, 1338.
3. J. JWO and R. M. NOYES, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **97**, 5422.
4. I. M. KOLTHOFF and R. BELCHER, "Volumetric Analysis", Interscience, New York, 1957, Vol. III, p. 370.
5. L. B. MØNSTED, O. MØNSTED and G. NORD, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1970, **66**, 936.
6. S. R. SAGI, K. A. RAO and M. S. P. RAO, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1983, **61**, 2795.
7. S. R. SAGI, K. A. RAO and M. S. P. RAO, *Talanta*, 1983, **30**, 282.
8. K. A. RAO, Ph.D. Thesis, Andhra University, 1991.
9. S. R. SAGI and K. V. RAMANA, *Talanta*, 1969, **16**, 1217
10. S. R. SAGI and M. S. P. RAO, *Talanta*, 1979, **26**, 52